

CONCEPT AND LANGUAGE WORLD VIEW

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Annotation: *This article presents opinions about the concept and its relation to the linguistic landscape of the world. The concepts of linguistic consciousness, concept and conceptosphere are explained from the point of view of the opinions of different scientists.*

Key words: *concept, linguistic consciousness, linguistic thinking, concept sphere, language landscape of the world.*

In most of the existing literature in linguistics, the concept concept is interpreted in connection with the concept of "view of the world". "View of the world" expresses a wide content, in our language, the unique aspects of the way of life of a person, the interaction of a person with the surrounding reality, nature and society, i.e. the world, the dialectic of existing relations in the dualism of man and the world. , in other words, it is one of the basic concepts that express the important aspects of a person's existence in the world. Man,

as a conscious being, acts in the center of events in nature and society. Therefore, this term interpreted in relation to a person is actively used in the field of humanitarian sciences. In the studies on the issues of worldview, linguistic consciousness, concept and conceptosphere, which are considered modern problems of linguistics, the worldview is based on scientific knowledge based on the views and interpretations of the person's attitude to the surrounding reality in the objective world. they associate the essence of events with

the content-ontological structure of the world, with complex structures. The development of cultural-typological research of mentality and the landscape of the world, the model of the world are interdependent universals that belong to such categories as space and time, cause and effect, the meeting of quantitative changes with qualitative changes in each culture. allows to draw conclusions about the composition of the set. A person relies on the image of the universe, which forms the basis of a person's worldview, with his social and cultural activities. Human communication and mutual understanding are impossible without the view of the universe. Naturally, the landscape of the world is clearly expressed in artistic concepts in our language. The speaker's observation and analysis of life events, coming to certain conclusions and expressing them artistically using the words available in the language form the unique style of the author along with the formation of an image of the artistic concept. The ability to express a person's character traits, inner world, various mental states caused by external influences in a way that the listener or reader can correctly understand and perceive in a person's life is clearly manifested in the texts. Therefore, the concept

concept is closely related to the text concept. A. Hojiev defines the term text as "Speech reflected by side-by-side letters, writing, in general, a fragment of speech; defines it as "text". According to M. Yoldoshev, in linguistics "...Speech is expressed as an event related to the speaker's speech process, and the text is a written ("reflected through printed letters") fragment of this speech event. ... "Speech" in its written form is equivalent to the term "text" ... The written form of any speech expresses the essence of the concept of text ... Text - oral speech, stabilized in relation to the context, certain rules and norms of literary language the written speech formed on the basis of... The text is a means of communication between people several centuries before and after, not at the same time. Among texts, artistic texts are distinguished by the breadth of possibilities for expressing ideas. The specific features of concepts are highlighted in artistic texts. Literary texts have the ability to illuminate, from the description of natural landscapes to the most subtle aspects of human relationships, in a way that will be remembered and influenced by the reader. Therefore, special attention is paid to imagery and emotionality in artistic texts. In artistic texts, the author uses colorful, impressive words and sentences in the

language in order to strengthen the aesthetic effect of the artistic concept. Visual means of the language create imagery and impressiveness in the artistic concept. This process is visible in communicative, perceptive and interactive structures.

In a communicative relationship, people exchange ideas, ideas, interests, moods, hooves, directions, etc. In the conditions of human communication, information and data are not only transmitted, but also formed, defined and developed. In this, each member of the communicative process observes the activity of the one cooperating with him. The partner is placed as a participating entity. Therefore, it is appropriate to take into account his interest, purpose and desire in the process of information transmission. However, the possibility of difficulties and various obstacles should not be ignored in this form of communication.

Interactive - (interaction) communication in the course of human interaction, it is important to establish not only the exchange of information, but also the exchange of actions, and the planning of common activities. Problematic situations that arise as a result of encountering opposite opinions and resistance are considered important

conditions for the activation of understandable processes in the context of communication. There is a multidisciplinary harmony, with an increasing need for additional information and data. This additional activity leads to an increase in the speed of interaction of the participants.

Perceptiveness - it is extremely important for the participants of the communication process to understand each other and to be able to explain to each other. Understanding each other can be interpreted in different ways: wanting a partner, understanding their goals and being able to direct their motives. Communication is a complex social-psychological process of interaction and mutual understanding between people, which is carried out using various tools. Each artist differs from each other in how they understand the facts of reality, how they treat and evaluate them, and what language units they use to describe them. The linguist M. Yoldoshev, who studied artistic texts, has the following points to cite: artistic text expresses the content of an artistic work, is functionally complete, formed on the basis of the image capabilities of language, and can freely combine various styles at the discretion of the author. , is an extremely complex whole that has the characteristic of

giving people aesthetic pleasure. In the literary text, as in the texts of other styles, laws such as strict logic, simplicity, comprehensibility, normativity are not fully followed. It effectively uses artistic image tools. Effectiveness comes to the fore. Melodic, catchy words are often used. In the depicted reality, a harmonious music and an inner harmony can be felt. It embodies many possibilities, such as stimulating a person spiritually, making him laugh, leading him to the world of imagination, immersing him in thoughts, forming his aesthetic thinking, and teaching him to look at events from a deep, different perspective. The artistic text, as is known, is formed based on the requirements and patterns of the artistic style, therefore poetic, romantic, solemn forms of expression are widely used in it. The choice of words, the structure of sentences, the use of lexical-semantic, rhythmic-intonational units also come from the requirements of this style. The most important of the linguistic features of the literary text is that it contains emotionally charged words, dialect words, historical and archaic words, slang and slang, figurative words, synonyms, forms, similar, pronounced and opposite words, as well as units such as idioms, proverbs and aphorisms are given ample space. It seems that the concept

concept appears in connection with the synchronic and diachronic state of the language, oral and written forms of speech, different forms of speech, poetic and prose texts, examples of oral creativity.

Depending on the concept of world view, concepts are considered to be the basic elements of human worldview and provide a strong connection of human morality and unity of knowledge in society. People communicate with each other through language, they influence or are influenced by each other in the form of spoken or written speech. Human communication can take place in the conditions where people understand each other and penetrate into their spiritual worlds, the crossing of spiritual worlds in people is at the expense of the common perception of the world for them. Disruption in understanding occurs in the change of the global view of the world, in the change of categorical collections, in the manifestation of a new image of the world. Each landscape of the world seals a certain image of the world in itself, manifests it by means of existing concepts in the language. The landscape of the world is perceived in the form of concepts in accordance with the vision of a certain reality, a certain logical understanding and imagination of the world.

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